

Inclusion of Life Skills in English Literature

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Abstract

Life skills are necessary for students of the twenty-first century. Graduate students are good at obtaining grades and ranks, but job opportunities tend to be scarce. Even though they are proficient in their subject matter, they lack the skills and qualities required for employability. Students should also develop their character qualities, such as their attitude and behaviour. We have a lot to teach our students not just in literacy, but also in life skills. According to the current situation, today's young brains do not take their lives seriously or properly care for themselves or maintain a healthy connection with their family, instructors, friends, and even neighbours. The instructor is the best individual to shape their thoughts and keep them on track. Literature may assist to address these injustices by teaching life skills and educating them to work and contribute to society.

Keywords: Life skills, literature, English language, attitude, and employable

Introduction

A corpus of written works is referred to as literature. Traditionally, the term has been used to describe visionary works of poetry and prose that are characterized by their writers' aims as well as the perceived aesthetic brilliance of their execution. Language, national origin, historical time, genre, and topic matter are only a few of the ways used to categorize literature.

According to the present circumstances, today's young minds do not take their lives seriously, do not take adequate care of themselves, and do not maintain healthy relationships with their family, instructors, friends, or even neighbours. The main objective of life- skills-education is to enable the learner to develop a concept of oneself as a person of worth and dignity. And meet out the challenging situations. In the educational system along with the teacher, it is the textbook that guides the students to the right path. Subjects develop abilities like problem-solving, logical reasoning power, and analytical attitude. From time to time, changes related to the teaching objective, its evaluation, and monitoring are equally important to fulfil the need.

As a teacher, we have the responsibility to mould the character, behaviour, and attitude of the student and persuade him to have a principled life, and even motivate him towards learning and acquiring knowledge and its application through hard work, farsightedness, determination, and discipline. Thus by gaining self-confidence to overcome

the hurdles that he is going to face in this learning process. Even we should be the source of his/her motivation and personality development. To justify it we can teach literature to a student which acts as the best resource for both the teacher and the student.

Review of Related Literature

Anderson (2005) aimed at evaluating the perceptions of students, teachers, and parents regarding the value of life skills and the Life long Guidelines Program due to the increase in the number of children committing extreme acts of violence prompting many schools to adopt and implement character education programs. The life skills and Lifelong Guidelines program focuses on producing a caring community of responsible citizens for life. Shawn (2014) conducted a study entitled "Look After Yourself, or Look After One Another? The study was an Analysis of Life Skills in Sport for Development and Peace HIV Prevention Curriculum. The purpose of this study was to conduct a critical discourse analysis, guided by the concept of bio pedagogies, of the Live Safe Play Safe (LSPS) manual that Right to Play (RTP) has used to train facilitators for its HIV/AIDS prevention program. The findings demonstrate that discourses of risk, individualism, and deficiency constructed life skills in a way that aligned with neoliberal approaches to health promotion and development, emphasizing risk management and individual responsibility, while glossing over the broader social and political factors influencing HIV transmission

Jinka Jyotsna, T.Dwarakanath (June 20180) explains in 'Teaching Life-Skills through Literature'? Literature is a term used to describe a written or spoken material. Broadly speaking, "literature" is used to describe anything from creative writing to more technical or scientific works, but the term is most commonly used to refer to works of the imaginative & creative, including works of poetry, drama, fiction, and nonfiction. Why should we teach life skills to the students of the twenty-first century? If we observe the present scenario of the students at both the Post-Graduate and Undergraduate levels, they are good at securing grades and ranks. But they are unable to become employable. Recent statistics say that only 15% of them can be employable. What about the remaining 85% of the students? Though they are good at their subject matter, they are not able to employability, to possess the required skills and qualities.

Life Skill

Life skills have been defined by the World Health Organization (WHO) as "abilities for adaptive and positive behaviour that enable individuals to deal effectively with the demands and challenges of everyday life".

They represent the psycho-social skills that determine valued behaviour and include reflective skills such as problem-solving and critical thinking, personal skills such as self-awareness, and interpersonal skills. Operationally, life skills in this study mean the availability of life skills with the ten categories or types

- 1) *Decision-making*
- 2) *Problem-solving*
- 3) *Creative thinking*
- 4) *Self-awareness*
- 5) *Interpersonal relationship skills*
- 6) *Empathy*
- 7) *Self-awareness*
- 8) *Empathy*

4) *Critical thinking*

9) *Coping with emotions*

5) *Effective Communication*

10) *Coping with stress*

Perusing writing educates us on these life abilities, and makes us more mindful of these life aptitudes.

Life Skills in English Literature

The English language is not only to develop literary skills but also to develop life skills through life lessons. It plays a significant role in daily life situations all over the world. It is an international language that is used in all aspects of life. It is the language of science, politics, economics, education, information, and technology. Accordingly, it is necessary to learn English as it is essential for communication and development (Hamdona, 2007). Keshta (2000) indicated that English is a universal language: the language of communication across countries in the international world of trade, business, air transportation, and technology.

Every author in English literature should and must consider the readers' life skills, such as social, societal, religious, political, and communicational issues. It draws readers into society and makes them active participants in real-life situations. By reading and understanding, individuals may better their status in life by solving difficulties, making decisions in stressful scenarios, strengthening their relationships, and being aware of their surroundings, for example. The literature, all of the instructors agreed, had the biggest impact on daily instruction.

Literature is used in a wide range of fields, from marketing and mass media studies to literature and rhetoric, ethnography and cultural studies, gender and age issues, sociology and political science, psychology and cognitive science, and so on, because it can be used to test and examine any piece of writing or occurrence of recorded communication. Furthermore, it has a positive association with sociolinguistics and psycholinguistics, and it is a key player in the creation of artificial intelligence.

In this paper, I have taken some examples from the works of a few authors, like Robert Frost's 'Stopping by the Woods on a Snowy Evening', 'The Road Not Taken', quotes from Buddha, and "If" by Rudyard Kipling.

Robert Frost's 'Stopping by the Woods on a Snowy Evening' is one of the most famous poems in American literature. In his poem, "If you've ever seen or experienced snow, you've probably taken a few minutes to marvel at its beauty. Possibly you were drawn to this element of nature that is at once soothing to look at and dark in its association with cold, winter, and the silence of nature. In literature, the seasons of nature are often used to explore the relationship between life and death, In between life and death,

"And miles to go before I sleep, And miles to go before I sleep"

Through his poetry, he teaches us to improve our life skills by fixing difficulties while we are trapped in between problems and enjoying our lives while we have Miles to go before we sleep. These poetry sentences have a profound significance that makes our lives more meaningful and aids in the development of life skills by allowing us to enjoy the current moment between life and death.

Also in "The Road Not Taken," Robert Frost, an American writer, allows himself to choose between two diverging paths. Our lives are dotted with moments when we must make our own decisions and no one can assist us. Each of us faces several forks on the road throughout our lives while success is never simple.

Even Buddha quotes,

*Do not believe anything anybody tells you,
including anything I tell you,
unless it agrees with your own experience and your common sense.*

In Buddha's own words, he explains how to live a life in the world of thorns. Buddha preached life skills, which we understand to be valuable.

To strengthen my understanding of life skills, I chose the poem "If" by **Rudyard Kipling**. This is one of the greatest poems written by John Kipling and is intended to serve as parental advice for his son. It is a noble and worthy life lesson. Every generation of all ages will find it suitable. It's a noteworthy piece of poetry that contains a lesson of value for almost everyone. Anyhow, it can be regarded as a set of virtues outlined by the poet that is conducive to the development of good human behaviour.

Kipling shows his readers the ideal way to act during times of dire crisis. He informs the readers to make themselves strong enough in a way that they can take responsibility for their choices and actions bravely and not indulge in the blame game. As he says,

*If you can keep your head when all about you
Are losing theirs and blaming it on you;
If you can trust yourself when all men doubt you,
But make allowance for their doubting too;
If you can wait and not be tired by waiting,
Or, being lied about, don't deal in lies,
Or, being hated, don't give way to hating,
And yet don't look too good, nor talk too wise...*

As a result, he wants the readers to study the value of life skills because they are crucial to the continuation of the life cycle in the modern world. According to the poet, faith is the most fundamental concept one needs to hold on to live a fulfilling life. He reminds us not to hate anybody or doubt anything. Is there a step-by-step guide to getting to the bottom of hell? Kipling also advises that defeat is not a defeat, it is a step toward success. Life is not perfect without defeat, and we cannot analyze our capabilities at odd times. He advises inviting defeat to learn another lesson. He urges his readers to have the courage to accept life's failures. Studying literature helps us develop this skill. In addition, he advises that success isn't easy, if one follows the precepts of life skills, one will fit in well with all sections of society.

If one adheres to the tenets of life skills will be able to blend in with people from all walks of life. This is a valuable life skill that can only be learned via reading. Reading literature teaches us these life skills, and makes us more aware of these life skills.

To sum up, literature will be a valuable tool for teaching and instilling life skills in today's youth to become true citizens of the country. Literature may assist to address these injustices by teaching life skills and educating them to work and contribute to society.

Conclusion

Life skills enable adolescents to live happy and successful life. Providing life skills education helps to build the foundation for learning the skills of individuals. A proper and relevant life skills education is needed for every youth to effectively adjust and participate in society. According to the current situation, today's young brains do not take their lives seriously or properly care for themselves or maintain a healthy connection with their family, instructors, friends, and even neighbours. The instructor is the best individual to shape their thoughts and keep them on track. Thus Literature may assist to address these injustices by teaching life skills and educating them to work and contribute to society.

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